

Preliminary guidelines for manual annotation of word senses in Latin and ancient Greek corpora

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November 2023

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Premise

In this document we define general guidelines for the annotation of lexical semantics (intended as the annotation of word senses) in a diachronic corpus of a historical language. Here we focus on Latin and Ancient Greek. This document is intended as a working document for a general description of this task and its related challenges. The guidelines were conceived within the CLARIN-funded project ‘A new CLARIN Resource Family for lexical semantic change research’, which spans from November

2022 to June 2023 and is led by Barbara McGillivray (King's College London) and Fahad Khan (ILC-CNR). The project aims at providing sufficient documentation for the creation of a new task-oriented CLARIN resource family (CRF) to support lexical semantic change research. Throughout the duration of the project, new versions of these guidelines will be released, with corrections and improvements based on further research. Beyond the scope of the CLARIN project, it is our intention to involve scientific communities working on this same task but applied to other languages, so as to increase the impact and interoperability of these guidelines.

It is important to specify that in these guidelines we assume that the annotation is performed manually and on a predefined list of target words.

This document is structured as follows. Section 1 describes the steps for setting up the annotation i.e. building the corpus (section 1.1), selecting the target words that should be annotated (section 1.2), setting up the sense inventory (section 1.3) and choosing the type of annotation (section 1.4). Section 2 is devoted to illustrating the steps that the annotators are expected to follow during the annotation task, including some linguistic challenges like metaphoric senses and vagueness. Finally, the Appendix contains additional documentation such as the list of target words used for these guidelines and the total corpus frequency counts of these lists, calculated on the Latin corpus LatinISE (McGillivray & Kilgarriff 2013).

1. Setting up the annotation

In order to carry out the type of annotation task described in this document, it is necessary to make some preliminary decisions and prepare the tools to perform the annotation. In this section we will discuss all the issues related to the annotation setup.

1.1. Source corpus

As mentioned in the Premise, we assume the general scenario where the sense annotation is aimed at carrying out diachronic analysis. In this framework, the annotation should be performed on a corpus representing

- a. different chronological stages of the language
- b. different textual genres
- c. different registers

The corpus should be as balanced as possible with respect to the different axes of variation chosen to select the texts. This is, of course, dependent on the particular context of the language in question and its available corpora.

The corpus needs to be annotated by lemma, part of speech (and optionally morphological information) to allow automatic retrieval of the target words selected for the semantic annotation and to facilitate the analysis by part of speech and lemma.

It is important to decide the type of format in which the corpus should be stored. The format can be e.g. XML, CoNLL-U depending on the type of annotation performed, or on the platform used for the annotation. The decision about the format should take into account the need to make the data available and easily accessible to the community of researchers working on similar tasks. Therefore, we recommend adopting a format that is considered a standard or is widespread enough in the community.

For the purposes of this document, we will focus on the LatinISE corpus (McGillivray & Kilgarriff 2013) for Latin and the Diorisis corpus (Vatri & McGillivray 2018) for Ancient Greek. These corpora

contain 13 and 10 million word tokens respectively, and have been (semi-)automatically lemmatised and part-of-speech tagged.

1.2 Target words

The annotator should be provided with a list of target lexical items to annotate. This list can be compiled based on a number of criteria, depending on the type of research questions that lie behind the creation of the annotated corpus. These guidelines in particular are conceived in order to create a dataset that would allow us and other researchers to define diachronic patterns of lexical semantic change and variation. In order to address this type of research questions, it is important that the list includes words that are known to have changed their meaning over time and based on their use in a specific linguistic and extra-linguistic context. The words selected for the annotation in this first draft of the guidelines and which we will use in the examples further in this document are taken from the medical and legal domains and from the lexical fields of anatomy and writing (see Appendix). These fields were selected because their lexicon is often concerned with semantic change. For instance, the use of technical terms in both medicine and law also depends on the development of the Roman legal system and on the innovations and new findings introduced in the medical field. The lexicon of these two domains of the Latin lexicon often includes terms that have developed a technical meaning drawing on a more common one. Consider sentences 1 and 2, both from the medical text *De medicina* by Celsus.

1. *Ex leguminibus vero valentior faba vel lenticula quam pisum.* (Celsus, *De medicina* 2, 18, 5) ‘Among pulses, beans or lentils are certainly more nutritious than peas.’
2. *Paene ineptiae sunt curare varos et lentículas et ephelidas* (Celsus, *De medicina* 6, 5, 1) ‘it is nearly useless to treat pimples, freckles and spots’

The word *lenticula* is used in sentence 1 to refer to the legume ‘lentil’ and in example 2 to refer to ‘freckles’. The second meaning is acquired by metaphorical extension based on the similarity between lentils and freckles (Langslow 2000: 187).

Choosing this type of words allows for a diachronic analysis aimed at determining how and in which linguistic circumstances the target words took on a new meaning which possibly replaced the preceding ones.

In addition, for comparison purposes, it is often useful to include in the list of target words polysemous words that are not particularly associated with any technical domain and that have high or medium corpus frequencies. Given their higher corpus frequencies compared with technical terms, manually annotating instances of these more general words is likely to help the development of automatic annotation systems.

1.3 Sense inventory

Each target word should be assigned an inventory of senses among which the annotator can choose the most appropriate for the word in the specific context. Such inventory can be created by using the lexicographic resources available for the language under study. For instance, in the case of Latin and Ancient Greek we can rely on the *Thesaurus Linguae Latinae* (1900–) and the Greek-English lexicon (Liddell & Scott 1940). The former is the richest Latin monolingual dictionary available and gives additional information about collocations, constructions and syntactic properties. However, the *Thesaurus* collects attestations only until 600 CE. Other resources for Latin are the Latin-English dictionaries *Oxford Latin Dictionary* (OLD; Glare 2012) and *Lewis and Short* (L&S; Lewis & Short

1879), the Latin monolingual *Thesaurus Linguae Latinae* (TLL), the 2016 edition of Gaffiot’s Latin-French dictionary (1934), the *Glossarium mediae et infimae latinitatis* (Du Cange 1883–1887), the *Dictionary of Medieval Latin from British Sources* (DMLBS; Latham et al. 1975-2013), and the neo-Latin-to-German digital dictionary *Neulateinische Wortliste* (Ramminger 2003–).

Another important resource to build the sense inventory is WordNet (Beckwith et al. 1991; Fellbaum 1998). It is available for many languages including Latin (Minozzi 2010), and the advantage is that its senses can be easily extracted automatically and used to build the sense inventory. Another advantage of using Latin WordNet (LWN) is that it is possible to add or modify the synsets associated with a word. The team of the project Lila (Passarotti et al. 2020) for instance is currently correcting a selection of words from LWN (see Litta et al. 2023).

The selection of the senses to be included in the inventory provided to the annotators should be made based on the desired granularity level. Comparing the lexicographic resources and WordNet allows firstly for the retrieval of all the macro-senses attested for the word over time, covering the entire diachronic span for historical languages. Then, the comparison of the sources can guide the selection of the level of detail in distinguishing the senses. Consider figure 1, which illustrates the selection of senses for the word *lenticula* ‘lentil’ but also ‘freckle’.

Figure 1. Selection of senses for the target word *lenticula*, gathered from different dictionaries and Latin WordNet (LWN).

1.3.1. Metaphorical senses

Previous work (see e.g. Fedriani et al. 2020; Buccheri et al. 2021) has annotated corpus occurrences of metaphors in Latin. Depending on the type of analysis planned, when building the sense inventory, the metaphoric senses of the target lemmas may be marked as such. The first step is to distinguish between literal and non-literal senses. The distinction can rely on the labels used in dictionary entries. Non-literal senses are generally marked in dictionaries with labels such as ‘transf.’, ‘fig.’ and similar. In rare cases the labels can be more specific, for example the *Thesaurus Linguae Latinae* sometimes uses labels such as *metaphorice* ‘by metaphor’ and similar. If relevant to the research questions, the senses listed as non-literal in the resources used to build the sense inventory should then be distinguished between metaphorical and non-metaphorical. An example of the use of such labels can be found the lexicographic description of *lenticula* (see examples 1 and 2) given by the Lewis and Short dictionary, where the meanings ‘lentil shape’, ‘a vessel shaped like a lentil’ and ‘freckle’ are

listed below the label ‘transf.’ (Lewis & Short 1879 s.v. *lenticula*). Based on the information given by the dictionary and on previous literature (Langslow 2000), we know that these three meanings can be considered metaphorical, as they originate from the resemblance of the referents with the shape and (in some cases) colour of a lentil. But the label ‘transf.’ does not include only metaphorical senses. For instance, the lemma *pupilla* in Lewis and Short is assigned three meanings: ‘an orphan girl’, ‘the pupil of the eye’ and ‘the eye’, of which the latter is labelled as ‘transf.’ (Lewis and Short 1879 s.v. *pupilla*). In this case, it is clear that the type of semantic extension observed for the meaning ‘the eye’ is not by metaphor, but rather by synecdoche and therefore this is not a metaphoric sense.

On the other hand, as shown by previous studies (Fedriani 2016; Fedriani et al. 2020 among others), metaphorical expressions can be described in cognitive terms using schemes that describe the process of mapping between a source and a target conceptual domains e.g. LOVE IS A MASTER (Buccheri et al. 2021). For such cases, refer to section 2.2.1.

1.3.2 Concrete and abstract senses

If relevant to the follow-up analysis, the meanings in the sense inventory can also be marked with respect to the features ‘abstract’ and ‘concrete’. Here we focus on a graded approach to annotation of abstract and concrete senses. In the graded approach presented in Brysbaert et al. (2013), the annotation of abstract and concrete sense is performed based on a scale from 1 to 5. Abstract words get score 1, and concrete words get score 5, according to a set of guidelines. They give the following instructions to determine the difference between a concrete word and an abstract word: “A concrete word [...] refers to something that exists in reality; you can have immediate experience of it through your senses (smelling, tasting, touching, hearing, seeing) and the actions you do [...]. An abstract word refers to something you cannot experience directly through your senses or actions” (Brysbaert et al. 2013:906). According to these guidelines, the word ‘justice’ would get score 1 (abstract), whereas the word ‘sweet’ would get score 5 (concrete). The in-between values can be assigned to words that can be experienced to some extent but that need an additional explanation in order to be understood (Brysbaert et al. 2013:906). An example is the concept of ‘square root’, which received a score of 3.12.

Adapting this guidance to the annotation of senses rather than words, we envisage that the annotators would need to determine whether a sense refers to something that exists in reality (and therefore should be marked as concrete) or to something that cannot be experienced directly through our senses or actions (and therefore should be marked as abstract). For example, in the case of *lenticula* (Fig. 1), all senses refer to things that exist in reality and therefore would be marked as concrete. On the other hand, *persona* can mean ‘mask’, ‘character in a theatre play’ or ‘legal person’. In this case, the first sense is clearly concrete, while the second satisfies the criteria for an abstract sense. The third sense may receive an intermediate score, as depending on the context it may refer to a specific person or to a more abstract entity.

1.4 Type of annotation

The annotation of senses can follow a binary or a graded approach. The annotator can be required to choose only one sense of the inventory that fits the context. This option can still account for contextual ambiguity by allowing the annotator to check multiple senses among which they cannot decide in a specific context.

Another option is to give the annotator the possibility to annotate each sense of the inventory associated with a target word with a scale from 1 to 4 (based on previous work by Schlechtweg et al. 2018). The annotator chooses for each sense a value from 1 to 4 depending on the sense expressed by

the target word in a specific context. Each degree is associated with a description of the type of relation between the sense of the inventory and the sense expressed by the target word in context.

- Degree 1: unrelated
- Degree 2: distantly related
- Degree 4: closely related
- Degree 4: identical

If the annotator is not able to determine if a sense of the inventory is related or not to the sense expressed in context, they can also choose the value ‘0’: cannot decide. The use of graded annotation has proven to be a successful approach in e.g. McGillivray et al. (2022) to deal with vagueness and ambiguity (see section 2.2.2).

2. Annotation task

2.1 Step 1

The annotator looks for the target words in the corpus by looking for the lemma of the target words provided e.g. see Appendix. The lemmas can also be automatically extracted from the corpus. In this case, the annotator will be presented with the sentences containing the target word to be annotated.

Depending on the annotation design and purposes, the sentences presented for the annotation may represent the total number of occurrences of the target word in the corpus, or just a selection.

2.2 Step 2

For each occurrence of a target word, the annotator is presented with an inventory of senses associated with the target word. The annotator assigns a value between 0 and 4 to each of the senses provided for the target word by looking at the context in which the word occurs.

During this step, the annotator may encounter some difficulties which are related to certain linguistic challenges. We will list below some of the aspects to which the annotator must pay particular attention when performing the annotation.

2.2.1 Metaphoric senses and metaphoric uses

In section 1.3.1 we have discussed the distinction between literal and metaphorical senses at the level of the sense inventory and mentioned that there might be cases in which a meaning that is not originally metaphorical can be used metaphorically in a specific context. An example of metaphoric use is the word ‘wound’ in the sentence “to cure the wounds of the world”, where ‘wounds’ is used metaphorically for the pain felt by people in the world (example taken from Montemagni et al. 2000). Other examples are “the *foot* of a mountain”, “the *leg* of a chair” (in Fortson 2003:649). Buccheri et al. (2021) provide numerous examples of metaphoric uses in Latin. Consider sentence 3, from Seneca’s *Epistulae* (from Buccheri et al. 2021:165).

3. *Una est catena, quae nos alligatos tenet, amor vitae.* (Sen. epist. 26, 10) ‘There is only one chain which binds us to life, and that is the love of life’

In this sentence, the noun *catena* ‘chain’ is associated with the concept *amor vitae* ‘love of life’,

building the metaphorical schema LOVE IS A BOND. The use of the noun *catena* to indicate a metaphorical bond is already described in lexicographic resources (see Lewis & Short 1879 s.v. *catena*), but depending on the research questions that motivate the annotation, it may be useful to annotate these metaphorical schemas as such. For this purpose, the annotation platform INCEpTION (Klie et al. 2018) for instance allows for the customisation of the annotation layers. Each sense may be assigned an annotation field called ‘metaphoric use’ which only accepts yes or no values that are selected based on the presence or absence of metaphoric uses of a meaning in the context.

2.2.2 Vagueness: determining sense boundaries

Previous work on lexical semantic annotation has shown that in some cases polysemous words can show a certain degree of vagueness among (some of) their senses (see McGillivray et al. 2022; Tuggy 1993 for an account of polysemy, ambiguity and vagueness). If the annotator cannot choose between two or more senses for a word in a given context, because all of them might be valid, it should be possible to select the same degree of relatedness e.g. 4 for the meanings involved.

Author contributions

PM is the main contributor of sections 1 and 2, analysed the Latin examples and compiled the word lists in Appendix A.1. BMcG contributed to the structure of this document, acquired the funding, reviewed and edited the drafts, and conducted the corpus analysis presented in the Appendix.

Appendix: Latin word lists and corpus frequency analysis

This appendix provides the lists of Latin target words used in these guidelines. We also report on a corpus frequency analysis conducted on the Latin corpus LatinISE (McGillivray & Kilgariff 2013) aimed at estimating the total corpus frequency counts of these lists.

The lists of Latin target words used in these guidelines were created based on two main criteria:

- (A.1) Polysemous words belonging to particular technical domains, relevant to the study of specific areas of the Latin lexicon. These words tend to have low to medium corpus frequency values. The sources for this selection were studies on Latin technical languages: see e.g. Collinet (1932); Schulz (1936); Birks (1997); Langslow (2000); de Meo (2005); Fögen (2011); Powell (2011); Roelli (2021).
- Polysemous words not associated with any technical domain but chosen in the high (A.2) and medium (A.3) corpus frequency bands.

The corpus frequency analysis of the lists above is described in sections A.1, A.2, and A.3, respectively.

We also extracted the list of lemmas in Latin WordNet from Litta et al. (2023). This list was manually curated by the LiLa project team by correcting and integrating the original content of Latin WordNet (Minozzi 2010). Its corpus frequency analysis is described in section A.4.

A.1. Words from technical domains

Medical domain

Causa, ieiunus, fistula, album, lenticula, impetus, plaga, cubitus, uterus, pubes, umerus, coxa, femur, stomachus, venter, ventriculus inferior, abdomen, alvus, fauces, guttur, praecordia, stomachus, thorax, venter, vertebrae, fel, duritia, durities, nigrities, eminentia, ventositas, nervositas, lenticula, via, porta, scrotum, anus, pupilla

Legal domain

Contractus, obligatio, occupatio, proprietas, derelectio, inaedificatio, specificatio, acquisitio, aequitas, distinctio, praesumptio, sponsio, fidepromissio, fideiussio, adpromissio, adstipulatio, absolutio, manus, persona

Lexical field of body parts

caput/testa, cerebrum/cerebellum, os/bucca, rostrum/beccus, sanguis/cruor/sanguem, testa, umerus/spatula

Lexical field of writing

Charta, epistula, codex, papyrus, torcular, arcus, bibliotheca(?), character, compingo, coopertorium, crudus, cudo, effigio, premo.

The individual frequency counts of the lemmas in the four groups above are available in the file “wordlist_latinise_4.xlsx” (tab “LatinISE_word_frequency_list”) by filtering on the column “in selected wordlist?” (C) for the value different from “no match”.

A.2 High-frequency words

The following list contains 30 high-frequency lemmas from the Latin corpus LatinISE (McGillivray & Kilgarriff 2013). They were selected from the list of the 1000 most frequent lemmas, excluding function words. The numbers following the lemmas (e.g. *dico*#2) refer to the homograph number in the Lewis & Short (1879) dictionary.

dico#2, *deus, habeo, multus, video, do, homo, idem, meus, dominus, verus, magnus, rex, dies, filius, locus, primus, pater, pars, modus, tempus, bonus, nomen, venio, terra, causa, corpus, fio, vir solus.*

The individual frequency counts of these lemmas are available in the file “wordlist_latinise.xlsx” (tab “LatinISE_word_frequency_list”) by filtering on the column “frequent lexical words” (D) for the value different from “no match”.

A.3 Medium-frequency words

The following list contains 30 medium-frequency lemmas from the Latin corpus LatinISE (McGillivray & Kilgarriff 2013). They were selected from the list of the 1000 most frequent lemmas, excluding function words.

Propositio, vulnus, sino, regia, diligenter, adhibeo, orator, promitto, integer, ardeo, consuetudo, liberi, cresco, futurus, iugum, color, victor, os#2, *adversus, desidero, iuvenis, testamentum, caeterus, condo, contemno, pontifex, iniquus, divido, mollis, moneo.*

The individual frequency counts of these lemmas are available in the file “wordlist_latinise.xlsx” (tab “LatinISE_word_frequency_list”) by filtering on the column “medium-frequency lexical words” (E) for the value different from “no match”.

A.4 Latin WordNet lemmas

Litta et al. (2023) contains a list of 8173 lemmas from Latin WordNet, whose synsets were manually corrected and integrated in the context of the LiLa project (Passarotti et al. 2020).

The individual frequency counts of these lemmas in LatinISE are available in the file “wordlist_latinise.xlsx” (tab “LatinISE_word_frequency_list”) by filtering on the column “LWN lemmas” (F) for the value different from “no match”.

Summary of corpus frequency analysis

		% frequency over total freq in LatinISE	% frequency over total freq of lexical words in LatinISE
total frequency of all lemmas in LatinISE	13,378,551		
total frequency of nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs in LatinISE (from wordlist_latinise_filtered)	7,731,576	57.79	
total frequency of words in wordlists	160,505	1.20	2.08
total frequency of frequent lexical words	689,090	5.15	8.91
total frequency of medium-frequency lexical words	49,543	0.37	0.64
total frequency of all selected words	899,138	6.72	11.63
total frequency of LWN lemmas	2,399,389	17.93	31.03

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